

Natural Convection Heat Transfer from Inclined Cylinders: a unified correlation

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Abstract : An empirical correlation for predicting the heat transfer coefficient for a cylinder under free convection, inclined at any arbitrary angle with the horizontal has been developed in terms of Nusselt number, Prandtl number and Grashof number. Available experimental data was used to determine the parameters for the proposed correlation. The proposed correlation predicts the available data well within $\pm 10\%$, for Prandtl number in the range 0.68-0.72 and Grashof number in the range $1.4 \times 10^4 - 1.2 \times 10^{10}$.

Keywords : heat transfer, inclined cylinders, natural convection, Nusselt number, Prandtl number, Grashof number

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